

Readability of visual and electronic leg tags versus rumen boluses and electronic ear tags for the permanent identification of dairy goats

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Key Words:	electronic identification, goat, leg tag, transponder

1 **INTERPRETATIVE SUMMARY**

2

3 **Leg tags for visual and electronic identification of dairy goats.** *By Carné et al., page*

4 Leg tags were evaluated throughout 12 mo in dairy goats. Rumen boluses, and visual and

5 electronic ear tags were also tested to allow for comparisons. According to circumference of

6 metatarsus, official leg tagging of goat kids was not recommended at 5 mo of age. In adult

7 goats, only the readability of leg tags (98.5%) and one type of attached transponder (98.3%)

8 fulfilled the official identification requirements (>98%); however, 1.5% of leg tags caused

9 limping. Suitable visual and electronic identification of dairy goats can be achieved with leg

10 tags, although further developments are required to allow tagging at early ages.

11 LEG TAGS VS. BOLUSES IN DAIRY GOATS

12

13 **Readability of visual and electronic leg tags versus rumen boluses and**
14 **electronic ear tags for the permanent identification of dairy goats**

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21 **ABSTRACT**

22 Murciano-Granadina dairy goats (n = 220) were used to assess the performance of leg tags
23 compared to other visual and electronic identification (ID) devices: 1) leg tags (LT) in the
24 shank of the right hind leg (metatarsus), and consisting of plastic bands (181 × 39 mm, 21 g; n
25 = 220) closed with 2 types of electronic button tags (ET1, 3.9 g, 26 mm o.d., n = 90; ET2, 5.5
26 g, 25 mm o.d., n = 130); 2) electronic rumen boluses (RB, 75 g, 68 × 21 mm, n = 220)
27 containing 32 × 3.8 mm transponders; 3) electronic ear tags (EE, button-button, 4.8 g, 24 mm,
28 n = 47); and, 4) visual plastic ear tags (VE; flag-button, 4.2 g, 40 × 38 mm, n = 220). All
29 transponders used half-duplex technology. Shank circumference of 47 replacement kids (5 to
30 6 mo of age) and 103 adult goats were measured to decide on the circumference of fastened
31 LT. Goats had been identified with rumen boluses and ear tags before starting the experiment.
32 Total time for leg tagging (LT application and transponder attachment), reading and data
33 recording with a handheld transceiver was measured. Readability [(read/readable) × 100] was
34 monitored for 1 yr with goats restrained in the milking parlor. Time and errors for reading RB
35 and ET2 in the milking parlor using the handheld transceiver were also recorded. Shank
36 circumference of kids (70 ± 1 mm) was 79.5% of those in adult goats (88 ± 1 mm); LT (107 ±
37 1 mm inner circumference) were only applied to adult goats, as were considered inadequate
38 for 5-mo kids. Time for leg tagging and data recording was 53 ± 3 s. At 1 yr, readability of
39 RB was 96.5%. No losses of LT occurred, although 3 (1.5%) had to be removed due to
40 limping, being LT visual readability 98.5%. Moreover, 7 (3.6%) LT were found open and
41 electronically unreadable due to loss or breakage of the button tag. Readability of button
42 transponders, excluding removed LT, was 93.9% for ET1, and 98.3% for ET2. For ear tags,
43 readability was 95.7 and 97.0% in EE and VE, respectively. Only LT and ET2 readabilities
44 differed. Reading time in the milking parlor was greater for RB (61.2 s) than for ET1 (45.9 s),
45 as well as reading errors (0.3 vs. 0%). In conclusion, leg tags were not adequate for the

46 identification of goat kids < 6 mo of age although, if adequately sized and fastened, this may
47 be an efficient method for adult goats under intensive conditions. Only leg tags with ET2
48 transponders met the ICAR requirements for official ID of adult goats (readability > 98%)
49 under the conditions of this experiment.

50 **Key words:** electronic identification, goat, leg tag, transponder

51

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INTRODUCTION

53

54 The European regulation CE 21/2004 on identification (**ID**) and registration of sheep and
55 goats, sets out a double ID system that includes the use of passive radio frequency ID (**RFID**)
56 devices in the Member States where total sheep and goat population surpasses 600,000
57 animals, as well as in goats where the total number is greater than 160,000. According to this
58 regulation, RFID has been officially deployable since 2005 although its compulsory
59 implementation has been adopted from January 2010 (CE 1560/2007). Regulation CE
60 21/2004 is already being deployed in Spain, where RFID rumen boluses have been in use
61 since 2006 (Real Decreto 947/2005).

62 Nevertheless, bolus retention in goats has proved to be highly variable (Caja et al., 1999;
63 Pinna et al., 2006; Carné et al., 2009a,b). For this reason, the use of subcutaneous transponders
64 in the fore- (metacarpus) or hind-leg (metatarsus) of goats was also proposed in goat herds
65 where poor bolus retention occurred. However, transponders injected in the leg have also
66 shown a wide range of losses and the use of small transponders is required (i.e., 10 to 15 mm),
67 which dramatically reduces their reading performance (MAPA, 2007; Carné et al., 2009a).
68 More difficult injection in the hind- than in the fore-leg has been observed in dairy goats
69 (MAPA, 2007).

70 Recently, European Regulation CE 21/2004 has been amended by Regulation CE
71 933/2008, which specifies the mandatory use of 1 visual and 1 electronic ID device
72 simultaneously. In this regard, rumen boluses and ear tags have eventually been established as
73 the authorized RFID devices whenever RFID is compulsory; visual ear tags and visual pastern
74 tags are accepted as the second ID device. Additionally, identification in the pastern by using
75 electronic marks (electronic leg tags) and injectable transponders has also been accepted in
76 sheep and goats whose first means of ID is a visual ear tag and if not leaving the Member
77 State of origin (CE 933/2008). Visual tags on the metatarsus are common for goat ID in the
78 milking parlor (Balvay, 2007) but, to our knowledge, no long-term reports on visual and
79 electronic leg tag readability are available. Thus, this work aimed at evaluating the visual and
80 electronic performance of leg tags placed on the metatarsus of dairy goats; rumen boluses,
81 and visual and electronic ear tags were also evaluated to allow for comparisons.

82

83

MATERIALS AND METHODS

84

85 Animal care conditions and management practices followed procedures stated by the
86 Ethical Committee of Animal and Human Experimentation of the Universitat Autònoma de
87 Barcelona (CEEAH 606/06), as well as the guidelines of the ICAR (2007) and the Spanish
88 Committee on Animal Electronic Identification (MAPA, 2007).

89

Animals, Management, and Identification Devices

90 A total of 220 adult Murciana-Granadina dairy goats from 1 commercial farm (Ramaderia
91 Huguet, Girona, Spain; n = 170) and from the experimental farm of the Universitat Autònoma
92 de Barcelona (S1GCE, Barcelona, Spain; n = 50) were used. All goats were born before 2005
93 and were not subjected to the new European Regulation EC 21/2004 on goat ID. Goats were

94

95 fed indoors with dehydrated ryegrass hay ad libitum (12% CP; as fed), 0.5 kg/d of alfalfa
96 pellets (17% CP; as fed), and 0.5 to 1.0 kg/d of commercial concentrate (1.53 Mcal of NE_L/kg
97 and 16% CP; as fed) according to the physiological stage. Additionally, goats from the
98 experimental farm grazed on cultivated Italian ryegrass pasture for 5 h daily (1000 to 1500 h).

99 All goats were visually identified with a leg tag (**LT**) consisting of a yellow plastic band
100 (weight, 21 g; length and width, 181 × 39 mm; and thickness, 2.2 mm; Animalcomfort,
101 Jumilla, Murcia, Spain) specially designed for goat ID (Figure 1), and with a buckle-like
102 closure system able to be adjusted to different inner circumferences. Each leg tag had a 3-digit
103 animal ID code printed for farm management purposes. The buckle's pin of the leg tags was
104 specially designed to be coupled with female ear tag pieces by using adapted tagger pliers
105 supplied by the leg tag manufacturer. Two types of button half-duplex (**HDX**) transponders
106 were used (Figure 1): **ET1** (weight, 3.9 g; o.d., 26 mm; open piece; n = 90; Allflex España,
107 Madrid, Spain) and **ET2** (weight, 5.5 g; o.d., 25 mm; closed piece; n = 130; Rumitag,
108 Esplugues de Llobregat, Barcelona, Spain). Transponder serial numbers included the
109 manufacturer code (Allflex, 982; Rumitag, 964) and worked at 134.2 kHz in agreement with
110 the International Organization for Standardization (**ISO**) 11784 and 11785 standards on
111 animal electronic ID (ISO, 1996a,b).

112 As European regulations lay down that animals must be officially identified no later than
113 6 mo of age, the metatarsus' circumference of 103 adult and 47 replacement (5 to 6 mo of
114 age) goats were measured to decide on the suitable inner circumference of leg tags to be used.
115 Subsequently, the inner circumference of 50 closed leg tags with the chosen closing
116 adjustment for adult goats was also measured to allow contrasts with leg circumferences
117 obtained.

118 Goats were also identified with standard size cylindrical boluses (**RB**; n = 220; weight,
119 75.0 g; length × o.d., 68 × 21 mm; and specific gravity, 3.4; Rumitag) made of atoxic,

120 nonporous and dense ceramic materials. These boluses were considered as control devices for
121 they had already been tested in previous studies (Pinna et al., 2006; MAPA, 2007; Carné et
122 al., 2009ab). Each bolus contained an ISO HDX, glass encapsulated transponder of 32 × 3.8
123 mm (Ri-Trp-RR2B-06, Tiris, Almelo, The Netherlands). Transponder serial numbers included
124 the 3-digit manufacturer code in agreement with corresponding ISO standards (ISO, 1996a,b).
125 Boluses were administered by trained operators as described by Caja et al. (1999) and Carné
126 et al. (2009b). This sort of bolus has been used since 2006 as the official RFID device for
127 sheep and goats in Spain (Real Decreto 947/2005).

128 As the use of button RFID ear tags has recently been regulated in Spain (Real Decreto
129 1486/2009), 47 goats were also tagged with 1 button-button HDX electronic ear tag (**EE**;
130 weight, 5.9 g; o.d., 24 mm; Allflex Europe, Vitré, France) attached to the left ear using tagger
131 pliers recommended by the manufacturer (Universal Total Tagger, Allflex Europe).
132 Transponders included the manufacturer code (Allflex, 982) and agreed to the ISO standards
133 therein (ISO, 1996a,b). Additionally, all goats wore 1 polyurethane visual ear tag (**VE**; flag-
134 button; weight, 4.2 g; flag piece dimensions, 38 × 40 mm; n = 220; Azasa-Allflex, Madrid,
135 Spain) on the right ear, with the button piece located on the inner side of the ear. Both pieces
136 of the tag had printed a 6-digit alphanumeric code aimed at compulsory official ID; these ear
137 tags were applied by Veterinary Service Officers.

138

139 *Measurements and Readings of Identification Devices*

140 Electronic devices were read in the milking parlor with ISO handheld transceivers (Ges
141 2S, Runitag) able to read ISO transponders at a least distance of 12 and 20 cm for ear tags
142 and boluses, respectively, as indicated in the European regulations on this issue (EC 21/2004;
143 EC 933/2008). Each RFID device was read immediately before and after administration to
144 check for breakages or electronic failures during administration, and in the case of RB, to

145 ensure their proper location in the reticulorumen. At the first post-tagging reading, the ID
146 code printed on the LT (3-digit numeric code for farm management) was typed and stored
147 into the transceiver. Time for leg tagging (band fastening and transponder attachment),
148 reading, and ID typing on the handheld transceiver was recorded. Leg tags and RB were read
149 at wk 1 to detect early losses or failures, and thereafter every mo until 1 yr. For VE, only 1
150 reading at the end of the study was carried out.

151 Performance of ID devices was expressed as readability (visual or electronic), being:

$$152 \text{ Readability} = (\text{no. read devices} / \text{no. readable devices}) \times 100$$

153 Breakage or damage of ear and leg tags was also recorded, as well as any incident during
154 the application of identifiers and the subsequent period of study. Additionally, the mechanical
155 resistance of the locking system of unused LT was measured in a sample of 5 button
156 transponders of each type. For this purpose, a computer-controlled force testing system
157 (MultiTest 1-i, Mecmesin Limited, Slinfold, United Kingdom) was used, and fastened LT
158 pieces were pulled at a constant displacement rate of 500 mm/min until breakage or
159 unfastening as indicated by the ICAR (2007) in the case of ear tags.

160 Comparison of reading performance between ET2 and RB in static conditions in the
161 milking parlor was also carried out. For this purpose, time for reading each device type in
162 groups of 24 goats in a double 12-stall parallel milking parlor (Westfalia-Separator Ibérica,
163 Granollers, Spain) was recorded. Before the measurements, check readings were done to
164 ensure that all devices to be read were functional. Time measurements were obtained by using
165 an electronic chronometer (Geonaute Trt'L 100, Decathlon, Alcobendas, Spain). For the
166 readings, a full-ISO handheld transceiver (Smart reader, Rumitag) connected to a 70-cm-long
167 stick antenna (GasISO, Rumitag) was used. A total of 30 groups of goats were read for both
168 ET2 and RB, therefore corresponding to 720 readings for each type of device. Reading
169 failures, and crossed readings (reading devices from adjacent goats) were registered as well.

170 We anticipated that a crossed reading of the bolus in the adjacent goat to the left might occur
171 if boluses were not located in the reticulum but in the rumen. Taking this fact into
172 consideration, and that current commercial handheld transceivers can be configured to prevent
173 duplicate registers during a reading control, readings were performed starting from the left
174 side of each milking stall to minimize the possibility of crossed readings with transponders
175 not read (from the contiguous goat to the right). Thus, a crossed reading of an adjacent goat to
176 the left was detected when the transceiver's display showed a message indicating that the last
177 read transponder had already been stored in the transceiver's internal memory. A crossed
178 reading of an adjacent goat to the right would be likewise detected because when moving to
179 the following goat, the transceiver would indicate that the device had already been read.

180 Dynamic reading efficiency of RB and ET2 attached to LT was also evaluated by using a
181 frame antenna (94 × 52 cm; Tiris, Almelo, The Netherlands) connected to a portable
182 stationary transceiver (model F-210, Rumitag) in groups of 22 to 35 goats passing through a
183 runway (width, 50 cm). Three antenna locations with respect to goat passage were tested:
184 vertical on the left side, longitudinal on the floor, and vertical with goats passing through it.
185 Dynamic reading efficiency was expressed as: (no. read devices /no. readable devices) × 100.

186

187 *Statistical Analyses*

188 Data on the shank and LT circumferences, and LT unfastening forces were analyzed by
189 ANOVA using the PROC GLM of SAS (version 9.1; SAS Inst. Inc., Cary, NC). For the
190 metatarsus circumference and the LT inner circumference, the model contained 1 effect with
191 3 categories (kid goats, adult goats, and leg tags), and the residual error. The model to
192 evaluate the unlocking force of LT contained the effect of the button transponder type (ET1
193 and ET2), and the residual error.

194 Readability of ID devices at 1 yr after tagging was analyzed with the PROC CATMOD of
195 SAS, and a Logit model with an estimation method of maximum likelihood (Cox, 1970) was
196 used. To compare the longitudinal readability of devices throughout the 1-yr study, the
197 Kaplan-Meyer non-parametric survival analysis and log-rank test of equality across strata (ID
198 devices) was performed with the PROC LIFETEST of SAS, as previously made by Fosgate et
199 al. (2006) and Carné et al. (2009a,b); the VE were not included in this last analysis as only 1
200 control at 1 yr was carried out.

201 Reading time of LT and RB in static conditions in the milking parlor was analyzed with
202 the PROC GLM; the fixed effect of device type (ET2 and RB), and the residual error were
203 considered. The PROC CATMOD was used for the evaluation of reading failures and false
204 readings in the milking parlor.

205 Least squares means of the dynamic reading efficiency of ET2 and RB, with the goats
206 passing through a runway, were obtained using the PROC GLM. Factors considered were the
207 3 positions of the frame antenna and the RFID device (ET2 and RB). Speed of passage of
208 goats through the runway was also analyzed with the PROC GLM, according to the antenna
209 position.

210

211

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

212

Application of Leg Tags

214 The metatarsal circumference of replacement Murciano-Granadina kid goats (< 6 mo) was
215 79.5% of that in adult goats (88 ± 1 mm), being the inner circumference of the fastened LT
216 107 ± 1 mm. It should be mentioned that Murciano-Granadina breed is described as a medium
217 frame dairy goat (bucks, 50 to 70 kg; does, 40 to 55 kg BW; ACRIMUR, 2010). According to
218 results, we considered that the metatarsal circumference of our replacement goats made

219 inappropriate the application of LT for permanent ID at this age, as tamper-evident LT fitting
220 the shank size of goat kids might eventually cause leg constriction in adult goats; therefore,
221 only adult goats were eventually included in the study of ID devices. In fact, 3 (2.5%) LT in
222 adult goats had to be removed because of limping; in 1 case the leg tag caused constriction of
223 the metatarsus of an inflamed leg, whilst in the other 2 cases the device was too loose-fitting
224 and slid down under the sesamoid bones, getting blocked between the sesamoid bones and the
225 hoof.

226 Abecia and Torras (2009) recently reported previous results on the suitability of Patuflex
227 leg tag (IRW Reyflex, 2010) application in Murciano-Granadina goat kids of 5 mo of age.
228 The authors also measured the metatarsal circumference of kids (76 mm, on average), slightly
229 greater than the value obtained in our kids, which was indicated to correspond to 86.7% of the
230 circumference in adult goats (88 mm, on average); yet, the inner circumference of fastened
231 leg tags was not specified, although it ranged from 106 to 127 mm depending on the fastening
232 adjustment. Displacement of leg tags under the sesamoid bones was also reported by Abecia
233 and Torras (2009) in a total of 6 (25%) kids, which made it necessary to relocate the ID
234 devices to their original position on several occasions. The authors suggested an age of 6 mo
235 for the application of leg tags in goats, which corresponded to 90% of adult metatarsal
236 circumference and 40% of adult BW. Taking these findings into account, accurate assessment
237 of the suitable inner circumference of leg tags for tagging at early ages seems critical to
238 prevent both the displacement of devices in young goats, and the possible leg damage due to
239 the tag pressing the leg in adult goats.

240 With regard to easiness of LT application in our study, overall time for leg tagging,
241 reading of transponder, and typing of ID data into the transceiver was 53 ± 3 s, on average.
242 This value is within the range of average time obtained with standard rumen boluses used in
243 adult goats of different breeds (52 to 55 s; Carné et al., 2009b).

244

245 ***Readability of Identification Devices***

246 At the end of the 1-yr study, 197 (89.6%) goats continued to be monitored. The remaining
247 23 goats died (n = 5) or were culled (n = 18) and replaced from the herd, these events not
248 being related to the experimental procedures. Readability of ID devices in the milking parlor
249 is shown in Table 1 and Figure 2; no readability progress of VE ear tags throughout the study
250 is shown in Figure 2 as only 1 control at the end of the study was carried out. Apart from the 3
251 LT that had to be removed because of limping, no losses or breakages occurred during the
252 experimental period. Nevertheless, 1 (0.5%) LT had the end of the band partially unfastened,
253 and slightly flapping out of the band's buckle, although button transponder was functional and
254 properly fastened. It can not be anticipated if the loose end of the LT in such an event might
255 lead to additional losses due to biting or to getting caught on the premises.

256 On the contrary, 7 RB losses were registered. Nonetheless, no difference between visual
257 readability of LT and readability of RB was detected (98.5 vs. 96.5%, respectively; $P =$
258 0.213). It should be mentioned that, on many occasions, LT had to be manually cleaned to
259 allow visual readability of the printed codes. Bolus readability remained within the wide
260 range of 92.0 to 99.6% reported at 1 yr after administration in goats identified with similar
261 bolus types (Capote et al., 2005; Pinna et al., 2006; Carné et al., 2009b).

262 With regard to button transponders, those corresponding to the LT that had to be removed
263 were not included in the Logit model analyses. At the end of the study no electronic failures
264 for ET1 and ET2 were detected. On the other hand, losses of ET1 were numerically greater
265 than those of ET2 (6.4 vs. 1.7%, respectively; $P = 0.110$), thereby resulting in a total button
266 transponder readability of 96.4%; as a consequence of button transponder losses, 3.6% LT
267 appeared open and electronically unreadable.

268 Unfastening force of LT by using ET1 button transponders was greater than with ET2
269 (421.4 ± 6.5 vs. 394.0 ± 3.8 N; $P < 0.05$), although both were above the threshold of 280 N
270 indicated by the ICAR (2007) for the unfastening or breakage of ear tags used for official
271 animal ID. Therefore, observed losses of ET1 and ET2 are likely to be preceded by the button
272 breakage; in fact, in 2 (1.7%) ET2 losses we observed parts of the button still attached to the
273 LT.

274 On the other hand, as the design of LT did not prevent their movements around the
275 metatarsus, the influence of the location of the attached transponder (lateral, medial, front, or
276 rear) on their breakage remains a topic for further research. The design of the LT used in our
277 study also allows encasing a glass-encapsulated transponder as alternative to the button
278 transponder; readability performance by using this sort of transponder should be thoroughly
279 evaluated as well. Available designs with the transponder encased in the plastic body of leg
280 tags (Hilpert et al., 2009; ITW Reyflex, 2009; ICAR, 2010) might also improve their
281 electronic readability, although no reports on readability are currently available.

282 With regard to EE, only 1 goat left the study before its conclusion. At 1 yr, 2 losses were
283 registered, thereby leading to a readability of 95.7%. Moreover, 1 EE occasionally failed.
284 Carné et al. (2009a) obtained 100% readability during a 3-yr study using similar button-button
285 RFID ear tags applied to replacement Murciano-Granadina kids. In fact, button ear tags were
286 suggested to reduce the occurrence of losses, given that flag-button RFID ear tags showed a
287 lower retention rate in the same experimental conditions (Carné et al., 2009a). In an 8-mo
288 large-scale study ($n = 2,620$), Schuiling et al. (2004) indicated 5.1% average losses in adult
289 goats identified with different types of RFID ear tags. Moreover, 1.6% electronic failures
290 were registered, obtaining a final readability of 93.3%. In addition, remarkable variability of
291 losses (0 to 7.1%) and electronic failures (0 to 2.9%) between herds was observed (Schuiling
292 et al., 2004), being our data within the aforementioned ranges.

293 Performance of compulsory official VE used in Spain at the time this work was carried
294 out was also evaluated at the end of the experiment. A total of 6 VE losses were registered,
295 thereby obtaining 97.0% retention. It must be stressed that damages in the flag piece were
296 observed in 24.9% of cases, 22.8% corresponding to the breakage of the flag piece right by
297 the base, making the VE appear as button-like devices. Nevertheless, only lost devices were
298 usually replaced by the veterinary officials during the annual blood sampling. The high
299 number of such findings might be related to an apparent good retention rate of these resulting
300 devices, especially considering the relatively low incidence of annual losses. In sheep,
301 retention of this same type of official ear tag averaged 96.7%, although no reference to
302 damages was made (Ghirardi et al., 2006).

303 According to our results, only the visual readability of LT and electronic ET1 differed (P
304 < 0.05) at the end of the study, corresponding respectively to the upper and lower readability
305 results obtained. Furthermore, only the LT visual readability and ET2 electronic readability
306 were greater than 98%, as recommended by the ICAR for extended field tests lasting 1 yr
307 (ICAR, 2007).

308 Results of estimated readability of ID devices, obtained with the Kaplan-Meyer survival
309 analysis, are shown in Table 2. This analysis permitted the incorporation of data
310 corresponding to goats that could not be monitored until the end of the 1-yr study. Differences
311 between factual and estimated readability were low, ranging from 0.1 to 0.5%; this was
312 mainly due to the high number of devices being monitored until the end of the study. As
313 previously observed for factual results, estimated values of ET1 electronic readability and LT
314 visual readability differed ($P < 0.05$). Moreover, ET1 and ET2 estimates tended to differ ($P =$
315 0.08). On the other hand, and similarly to factual data, no differences ($P > 0.1$) between LT,
316 RB and EE were detected.

317

318 *Static Reading Efficiency of Leg Tags and Boluses in the Milking Parlor*

319 Results referring to reading efficiency of leg tags with electronic transponders (ET2) and
320 RB in static conditions from the pit side in the milking parlor are shown in Table 3. Because
321 of the distance between EE and the operator placed in the pit of the milking parlor, EE
322 reading was not possible. Reading time of ET2 in the milking parlor was 25% lower ($P <$
323 0.001) than for RB. Lower time required for LT reading was mainly caused by an easier
324 access to the ET2 from the rear position of the animal, with the operator located in the pit of
325 the milking parlor. This fact also allowed a quicker transition between goats. In the case of
326 RB, the stick antenna had to be positioned close to the cranial left-side abdominal area, as
327 boluses have been described to remain mainly located in the reticulum of domestic ruminants
328 (Garín et al., 2003; Castro et al., 2004; Antonini et al., 2006).

329 With regard to unitary reading time in the milking parlor, the average value obtained for
330 RB (Table 3) read from the rear of the goats was within the range of 2.4 to 4.0 s reported by
331 Caja et al. (1996) for boluses administered to dairy sheep, and in a similar milking parlor. On
332 the contrary, our unitary reading times of ET2 attached to the leg tags were lower than those
333 of RB ($P < 0.001$; Table 3). In the same way, low unitary reading times of electronic ear tags
334 (1.9 to 2.8 s) were reported in dairy sheep read from the front in the milking parlor, as the
335 transponder was quickly localized by sight (Caja et al., 1996).

336 In the case of RB, we anticipated that crossed readings of the bolus in the adjacent goat to
337 the left might take place whenever the boluses were not located in the reticulum but in the
338 rumen. For this reason, readings were performed starting from the left side of each stall, in
339 order to minimize the possibility of crossed readings with transponders not read
340 (corresponding to the contiguous goat to the right). As already mentioned in the material and
341 methods section, this detail is of major relevance as current commercial transceivers can be
342 configured so that no duplicate readings are registered in a reading session; thus, if the goat to

343 the left was wrongly read, the transceiver's screen would display that the transponder had
344 already been registered. In such an event, the operator would only have to perform a new
345 reading attempt of the transponder expected to be registered. In this regard, 2 such cases were
346 observed in our experiment, supposing 0.3% of overall bolus readings. As anticipated, no
347 crossed reading with goats to the right in the milking parlor occurred. Crossed readings might
348 take place if intending to read a goat which had lost the rumen bolus. In addition to crossed
349 readings, in 3 (0.4%) cases the transceiver was unable to read the RB after having the
350 electromagnetic field activated for 2 s (as previously configured in the transceiver settings); in
351 these cases, successful readings were accomplished at the second reading attempt. Ait-Saidi et
352 al. (2008) indicated 0.6% of reading errors in similar experimental conditions when carrying
353 out semi-automated milk recordings, although the nature of these reading anomalies was not
354 specified. In our work, the aforementioned reading methodology and transceiver
355 configuration to avoid duplicate recording, prevented mistaken assignation of the transponder
356 to a different goat; in such conditions, reading errors only caused an increment in the average
357 reading time required per goat.

358

359 *Dynamic Reading Efficiency of Leg Tags and Rumen Boluses*

360 Results of dynamic reading performance of RB and ET2 in a runway, according to the
361 position of the frame antenna, are shown in Table 4. The speed of passage of goats through
362 the runway was lower ($P < 0.05$) when goats were forced to pass through the antenna, as
363 goats tended to slow down just before crossing it. Nevertheless, the speed of passage was in
364 all cases lower than 1 goat/s, which comes to terms with conditions for proper dynamic
365 reading according to previous reports (JRC, 2003; Ghirardi et al., 2006b). Goats in our study
366 wore both RB and ET2 transponders (estimated distance between transponders 30 cm), which
367 led to the worst condition possibly faced when reading herds identified with several types of

368 RFID devices. In such conditions, the incidence of reading collisions due to the presence of
369 more than 1 transponder at a time inside the electromagnetic field generated by the transceiver
370 were maximized; this fact was expected to cause an increment of transponder's reading
371 failures. Results of dynamic reading efficiency according to the position of the frame antenna
372 in the runway (Table 4) showed that the greatest reading efficiency was obtained with RB
373 read with the antenna located laterally to the left of the runway. The following best
374 efficiencies were obtained with RB when goats had to pass through the antenna, as well as for
375 ET2 read with the antenna placed on the floor. According to our results, no antenna location
376 offered maximum reading performance for both types of devices. In fact, the best antenna
377 position for ET2 reading was likewise the worst option for proper RB reading. These findings
378 should be taken into account if dealing with goat herds where different RFID devices are in
379 place, as allowed by current Europe regulations (CE 21/2004 and CE 933/2008). As
380 anticipated, the collision occurrence in our experiment reduced the reading efficiency of
381 devices, as sheep and goats just identified with standard-sized electronic boluses, and under
382 similar reading conditions, yielded average dynamic reading efficiencies > 99% (Ghirardi et
383 al., 2006b). Likewise, the only reference available, to our knowledge, on the dynamic reading
384 efficiency of rumen boluses by using a frame antenna located on the floor of a runway (no
385 details available on the transceiver technical features) yielded 74.2% (MAPA, 2007), which is
386 greater than the value obtained in our study.

387 With regard to the performance of transponders attached to leg tags, no literature on their
388 dynamic reading efficiency is available. Nevertheless, an average dynamic reading efficiency
389 of 99.7% has been reported when using 15-mm transponders injected in the foreleg pastern of
390 Murciano-Granadina adult goats and the transceiver's antenna placed on the floor (MAPA,
391 2007).

392 In our study, only RB read with the lateral antenna reached the 95% minimum dynamic
393 reading efficiency recommended by MAPA (2007) for sheep and goat ID on field conditions.
394 This recommended minimum value allows > 99.7% readability of electronic devices when 2
395 consecutive readings of the same herd are performed and the obtained ID data files are
396 combined. For LT and RB in our study, final readability values of 99.4 and 99.8% would be
397 obtained if 2 consecutive readings were performed with the antenna placed on the floor or
398 laterally, respectively.

399

400

CONCLUSIONS

401

402 Leg tags in the hind leg of adult goats offered a suitable (> 98%) visual and electronic
403 readability, if adequate button transponders are used. Nevertheless, both design and inner
404 circumference of fastened leg tags should be evaluated in thorough detail to avoid limping
405 and prevent other derived damages. This is also the case of early leg tag application in
406 replacement stock. In this study, standard-sized rumen boluses and electronic ear tags did not
407 reach the recommended readability (> 98%) for official identification of goats as a
408 consequence of losses, which should be reduced.

409

410

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For Peer Review

495 **Table 1.** Readability of leg tags, rumen boluses, and visual ear tags in adult dairy goats during a 1-yr study¹

Item	LT	Button transponders			RB	Ear tags	
		ET1	ET2	Overall		EE	VE
Applied, n	220	90	130	220	220	47	220
Monitored, n	197	78	116 ²	194 ²	197	46	197
Removed, n (%)	3 ³ (1.5)	0	0	0	—	0	0
Lost, n (%)	0	3 (3.9)	2 (1.7)	5 (2.6)	7 (3.5)	2 (4.3)	6 (3.0)
Damaged, n (%)	0	2 ⁴ (2.6)	0	2 (1.0)	0	0	49 (24.9) ⁵
Readability, %	98.5 ^a	93.6 ^b	98.3 ^{ab}	96.4 ^{ab}	96.5 ^{ab}	95.7 ^{ab}	97.0 ^{ab}

496 ^{a,b}Within a row, values with different superscripts differ ($P < 0.05$).

497 ¹Devices: LT = plastic-made leg tag with a 3-digit code printed for individual visual identification (weight, 21 g; length × width, 181 × 39 mm;
498 and thickness, 2.2 mm; Animalcomfort, Jumilla, Murcia, Spain); ET1 = half-duplex button transponder (weight, 3.9 g; o.d., 26 mm; Azasa-
499 Allflex, Madrid, Spain) attached to LT; ET2 = half-duplex button transponder (weight, 5.5 g; o.d., 25 mm; Rumitag, Esplugues de Llobregat,
500 Barcelona, Spain) attached to LT; RB = ceramic-made rumen bolus (weight, 75 g; length × o.d., 68 × 21 mm; encasing a 32-mm half-duplex
501 glass-encapsulated transponder; Rumitag); EE = half-duplex electronic button-button ear tag (weight, 5.9 g; o.d., 24 mm; Azasa-Allflex); VE =
502 visual ear tag for official use (weight, 4.2 g; flag dimensions, 38 × 40 mm; Azasa-Allflex).

503 ²Button transponders attached to the 3 leg tags removed were excluded from the Logit model analyses.504 ³Removed because of limping: 1 leg tag caused constriction of an inflamed leg; 2 leg tags got blocked between the sesamoid bones and the hoof.505 ⁴Damaged devices were unreadable.

506 ⁵Breakage of the flag part in 45 (22.8%) ear tags was observed, resulting in button-like devices; all printed codes on the button piece were
507 visually readable.

508 **Table 2.** Estimated readability of identification devices with Kaplan-Meier non-parametric survival analysis and log-rank tests between devices
 509 in dairy goats throughout 1 yr of study

Item	LT	Button transponders			RB	EE
		ET1	ET2	Overall		
Applied, n	220	90	130	220	220	47
Censored data, n ²	23	12	14	26	23	1
Events, n ³	3	5	2	7	7	2
Readability estimates, %	98.6 ^a	94.1 ^{bx}	98.4 ^{aby}	96.7 ^{ab}	96.6 ^{ab}	95.7 ^{ab}

510 ^{a,b}Within a row, values with different superscripts differ ($P < 0.05$).

511 ^{x,y}Within a row, values with different superscripts differ ($P < 0.10$).

512 ¹Devices: LT = plastic-made leg tag with a 3-digit code printed for individual visual identification (weight, 21 g; length × width, 181 × 39 mm;
 513 and thickness, 2.2 mm; Animalcomfort, Jumilla, Murcia, Spain); ET1 = half-duplex button transponder (weight, 3.9 g; o.d., 26 mm; Azasa-
 514 Allflex, Madrid, Spain) attached to LT; ET2 = half-duplex button transponder (weight, 5.5 g; o.d., 25 mm; Rumitag, Esplugues de Llobregat,
 515 Barcelona, Spain) attached to LT; RB = ceramic-made rumen bolus (weight, 75 g; length × o.d., 68 × 21 mm; encasing a 32-mm half-duplex
 516 glass-encapsulated transponder; Rumitag); EE = half-duplex electronic button-button ear tag (weight, 5.9 g; o.d., 24 mm; Azasa-Allflex).

517 ²Devices which left the study before 1 yr without an event being registered.

518 ³Unreadable devices.

519 **Table 3.** Comparison of static reading efficiency of electronic leg tags (ET2 transponders)
 520 and rumen boluses in dairy goats in the milking parlor (values are least squares means \pm SE),
 521 by using handheld transceiver connected to a stick antenna¹

Item	Device ²		<i>P</i> <
	Bolus	ET2	
Readings, n ³	720	720	—
Group reading time, s/24 goats ⁴	61.2 \pm 1.0	45.9 \pm 0.7	0.001
Unitary reading time, s/goat	2.6 \pm 0.1	1.9 \pm 0.1	0.001
Static reading efficiency			
Reading failures, n	0	0	— ⁶
False readings, n ⁵	2 (0.3%)	0	— ⁶
Readability, %	99.7	100	— ⁶

522 ¹Smart Reader (Rumitag, Esplugues de Llobregat, Barcelona, Spain) connected to a 70-cm
 523 stick antenna.

524 ²Devices: RB = ceramic-made rumen bolus (weight, 75 g; length \times o.d., 68 \times 21 mm;
 525 encasing a 32-mm half-duplex glass-encapsulated transponder ; Rumitag); ET2 = half-duplex
 526 button transponder (weight, 5.5 g; o.d., 25 mm; Rumitag) attached to a leg tag.

527 ³Number of read devices, carried out in groups of 24 goats in the milking parlor.

528 ⁴Groups of 24 goats in a double-12 stall parallel (side by side) milking parlor.

529 ⁵Reading of transponders from adjacent goats in the milking parlor.

530 ⁶No statistical contrasts could be carried out when no reading incidences or 100% readability
 531 were registered.

532 **Table 4.** Dynamic reading efficiency¹ (DRE) of electronic rumen boluses and button transponders attached to leg tags in dairy goats, according
533 to the position of the transceiver's antenna^{2,3}

Antenna position	Speed of passage, goats/min	RB		ET2		<i>P</i> <
		N	DRE, %	N	DRE, %	
Lateral	54 ± 3.7 ^a	495	95.2 ± 1.7 ^a	525	68.2 ± 3.4 ^c	0.001
Floor	49 ± 3.2 ^a	495	16.0 ± 1.3 ^b	525	92.4 ± 1.9 ^a	0.001
Passing through	40 ± 3.1 ^b	363	93.0 ± 1.9 ^a	385	83.4 ± 1.5 ^b	0.001

534 ^{a,b}Within a column, values with different superscripts differ (*P* < 0.05).

535 ¹Using a frame antenna (94 × 52 mm; Tiris, Almelo, The Netherlands) connected to an F-210 portable stationary transceiver (Rumitag,
536 Esplugues de Llobregat, Barcelona, Spain), in goats passing through a runway (width, 50 cm); DRE = (no. read devices/no. readable devices) ×
537 100.

538 ²Devices: RB = ceramic-made rumen bolus (weight, 75 g; length × o.d., 68 × 21 mm; encasing a 32-mm half-duplex glass-encapsulated
539 transponder ; Rumitag); ET2 = half-duplex button transponder (weight, 5.5 g; o.d., 25 mm; Rumitag) attached to a leg tag.

540 ³Reading sessions carried out in groups of 22 to 35 goats.

541 **Figure 1.** Leg tags and attached transponders for the visual and electronic identification of
542 dairy goats in the hind leg. Abbreviations: LT = plastic-made leg tag with a 3-digit code
543 printed for individual visual identification (weight, 21 g; length × width, 18 × 4 cm; and
544 thickness, 2.2 mm; Animalcomfort, Jumilla, Murcia, Spain); ET1 = half-duplex open button
545 transponder (weight, 3.9 g; o.d., 26 mm; Azasa-Allflex, Madrid, Spain) attached to LT; ET2 =
546 half-duplex closed button transponder (weight, 5.5 g; o.d., 25 mm; Rumitag, Esplugues de
547 Llobregat, Barcelona, Spain) attached to LT.

548
549 **Figure 2.** Evolution of readability of identification devices throughout 1 yr of study in dairy
550 goats: LT (■), RB (●), ET1 (▲), ET2 (△), and EE (◆). Abbreviations: LT = plastic-made leg
551 tag with a 3-digit code printed for individual visual identification (weight, 21 g; length ×
552 width, 181 × 39 mm; and thickness, 2.2 mm; Animalcomfort, Jumilla, Murcia, Spain); ET1 =
553 half-duplex open button transponder (weight, 3.9 g; o.d., 26 mm; Azasa-Allflex, Madrid,
554 Spain) attached to LT; ET2 = half-duplex closed button transponder (weight, 5.5 g; o.d., 25
555 mm; Rumitag, Esplugues de Llobregat, Barcelona, Spain) attached to LT. RB = ceramic-made
556 rumen bolus (weight, 75 g; length × o.d., 68 × 21 mm; Rumitag); EE = half-duplex electronic
557 button-button ear tag (weight, 5.9 g; o.d., 24 mm; Azasa-Allflex).

558 **Figure 1.**

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560 Figure 2.

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